

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Report on (re-)manufacture of the innovative nonwoven products.

Document Information

Report name	Report on (re-)manufacture of the innovative nonwoven products.
Version number	2.0
Document number	D4.3
Due date for deliverable	31/05/2020
Actual submission date	29/05/2020
Lead beneficiary	Technoplants

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730456

DOCUMENT CONTROL PAGE

Work Package	WP4 (D4.3)
Lead Authors (Org)	Sara Gualtieri (TP)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Daniele Spinelli (NTT)
Reviewers (Org)	Daniele Spinelli (NTT)
Due Date	May 2020
Date	29/05/2020
Version	2.0

Dissemination level

PU: Public	X
PP: Restricted to other programme participants	
RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium	
CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
1	02/05/2020	Sara Gualtieri	Deliverable structure preparation
2	20/05/2020	Daniele Spinelli	Contributions from NTT added
3	22/05/2020	Daniele Spinelli	Final review
4	29/05/2020	Daniele Spinelli	Review after coordinator's comments
5	09/12/2020	Sara Gualtieri	Updates and final review

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of Contents

1 Executive Summary	8
2 Introduction	9
2.1 Shredding step	9
3 Nonwovens re-manufacturing through airlay technology by TP	12
3.1 Description of (re-)manufacturing technology used to produce the materials	12
3.2 Sustainable binders for non wovens layers realization	14
3.3 Technical aspects related to polyester fibers for non wovens	15
3.4 Key characteristics for non wovens fibers	16
4. Conclusions and final recommendations	17
5. Next steps	18
6. References	18

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Equipment for non wovens shredding..	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 2 - Polyester fibers after shredding step...	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 3 - SEM images of polyester fibers before (a) and after shredding step (b).....	11
Figure 4 – Non wovens layers glued by (A) GREEN LINE and (B) SILANBLOCK (B) binders.....	14

List of Tables

Table 1 – Tensile strength (MPa) of Sample B re-manufacturing cycles at different ratio virgin vs recycled fibers	12
Table 2 – Table 2 – Tensile strength (MPa) for Sample C re-manufacturing cycles at different ratio virgin vs recycled fibers.....	13
Table 3 – Mechanical properties for non wovens layers realization respect to conventional materials (thickness 3 mm).....	15

Acronyms and abbreviations

RPL	Recycled polyester
VPL	Virgin polyester
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy

1 Executive Summary

The deliverable brings an overview of the remanufacturing process for non-wovens intermediate product developed by airlaid technology and thermal compression as reported in D3.2. Using the result of the nonwoven layers produced within WP3, automotive, building and furniture nonwoven applications designed in the WP2 have been manufactured by optimizing the fibre air-lay and compression technology.

Process conditions have been optimised in terms of:

- heating temperature and treatment time to allow a complete melting of the thermoplastics and to assure that the fibres are not degraded and ensure the expected mechanical performance of the non-woven composites
- the amount of recycled fibers for (re-)manufacturing using at least 90% of recycled fibers and recovered fiber length has been evaluated for the cascade application.
- (Re-)processing guidelines as well as material data sheets have been defined according to the final applications.

2 Introduction

Nonwoven waste of e.g. spunlace type can be recycled by melting it down into plastic granulate which can be used for production of new synthetic fibres. This presupposes that the waste is constituted by relatively "clean" synthetic material based on thermoplastic synthetic fibres. One example is recycling of polyester from bottles for producing polyester fibres which are used for carpet manufacture.

It is also known to mechanically shred nonwoven and textile waste and to use the freed recycled fibres. In this case, mixed waste comprising both synthetic and natural fibres can even be used. New materials for, for instance, sound insulation, filters and geotextiles can be produced from the recycled fibres by thermobinding, needling or adhesive binding. By the addition of a suitable binder via impregnation, spraying, application of a coat or the like, certain properties such as wet strength and dry strength of the material can be additionally improved.

A large portion of the production waste from nonwoven manufacture however presently goes to dumps as landfill or to waste incineration plants. Such production waste emanates from edge-trimming of the material webs, start-up waste and material which is discarded for various reasons. To the nonwoven waste is added used material as well as production waste.

This report describes the re-manufacturing process related to intermediate materials developed by airlay technology and their properties that will affect the design and manufacture of components for automotive, furniture and building sector.

The materials and their re-manufacturing processes developed by the project partners NTT and TP, will be described in terms of panels downsizing and fiber feed for airlaid technology. All the material properties will be tested and compared to the first manufacturing routes, as well as the percentage of recycled fibers.

2.1 Shredding step

The single double shaft shredder/shredding machine adopted advanced technologies, it is mainly used to shredder soft plastic, such as PP/PE/HDPE film, plastic bag, wove bag or Non-wovens, Jumbo bags and so on. The production capacity can reach up to 10,000 kg / hour, depending on the type of material to be cut and the cut length thereof.

Figure 1 – Equipment for non wovens shredding (150-250 kgs/hr).

The material is transferred by the conveyor belt towards the feeding section (pair of feed rollers or dish plate type depending on the materials to be recycled) and compacted by the feed pressing roller. The feeding section feeds the material to the main cylinder (different configurations available depending on the material to be recycled) and hold the fibres tightly by means of air cylinders, thus maximising the opening effect on the fibres. The fiberized material is then delivered to the following machine by the hopper and a downstream motorfan.

The following prototypes have been selected for re-manufacturing steps:

1) SAMPLE B (car door panel insulation)

Material: polyester (100%) (thermal bonding)

Height: 40 mm

Weight: 1075.9 g/m²

2) SAMPLE T (car floor liner; internal building covering, panels for shelves and/or desk top)

Material Sample C: polyester (70%) + wood scraps (30%) (thermal bonding)

Height: 30 mm

Weight: 2304.4 g/m²

Rigid panels were obtained by thermal compression at 210°C for 20 min of a three-layer structure: Sample C + Sample B + Sample C.

The materials were selected in a preliminary stage as the best candidates to produce the final prototypes using non-wovens realized with natural and synthetic fibers to reach the market technical requirements: SAMPLE B (volumetric mass, compression set, flame resistance, thermal resistance and conductivity) and SAMPLE T (tensile strength, thermal conductivity, lateral nail resistance and screw withdrawal).

The recycled material from shredding process comprises fibres with a fibre length of between 5 and 60 mm and a fineness of between 0.1 and 20 dtex (Figure 2). SEM analysis was performed in order to investigate the fibers structure before the mechanical shredding of soft and rigid panels.

Figure 2 – Polyester fibers after shredding step.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3 – SEM images of polyester fibers before (a) and after shredding step (b).

SEM images reported in Figure 3 shown the break fiber zones after the mechanical shredding steps. This evidence could also affect the mechanical properties of the fibers for their reuse in re-manufacturing cycles.

3 Nonwovens re-manufacturing through airlay technology by TP

3.1 Description of (re-)manufacturing technology used to produce the materials

Shredded fibers were fed directly in airlaid equipment and mixed with different percentage of virgin fibers to form a new fiber web. Virgin fibers were added in the airlaid equipments by the ratio polyester/wood scraps 70%/30% as for the original formulation.

The advantage of this is that the composition of the recycled fibres and the other raw material fibres is the same, which ensures an even quality in the produced material.

However, as previously mentioned, the recycled fibres may be constituted by other nonwoven and textile waste and the produced material can be either wholly, or only partially, based on recycled fibres.

Table 1 and Table 2 report tensile strength value as reference parameter in terms of physical and mechanical properties preservation after three re-manufacturing cycles.

Table 1 – Tensile strength (MPa) of Sample B re-manufacturing cycles at different ratio virgin vs recycled fibers.

Sample composition	1st cycle	2nd cycle	3rd cycle
100% RPL	37.8	20.1	16.2
90% RPL / 10% VPL	22.4	20.8	18.7
80% RPL / 20% VPL	27.3	25.6	21.8
70% RPL / 30% VPL	31.6	30.1	29.7
60% RPL / 40% VPL	35.9	35.1	34.9

Table 2 – Tensile strength (MPa) for Sample C re-manufacturing cycles at different ratio virgin vs recycled fibers.

Sample composition	1st cycle	2nd cycle	3rd cycle
100% R	19.7	13.0	11.2
90% R / 10% V	9.8	8.4	7.6
80% R / 20% V	11.3	10.1	9.6
70% R / 30% V	14.8	13.7	12.8
60% R / 40% V	19.3	18.9	18.7

With the mechanical tearing of the waste material, the freeing of the fibres is often incomplete So that the recycled fibres can be present partly in the form of flocks. These flocks give non-uniformities in the produced material, which have certain positive effects like the material having a more textile-like appearance and, in the case where the material is to be used as drying material, the cleaning capacity of the material is increased due to the mechanical friction effect which the non-uniformities produce. A negative effect is however that the non-uniformities in the material can cause reduced Strength. For applications where Strength is important, this can be increased by the addition of a suitable binder or wet-strengthener. Examples of conventional compounds are polyamide-epichlorohydrin, EVA, butadiene-Styrene, latex etc. The addition of binder can occur in a known manner by impregnation, Spraying, application of a layer or the like. A suitable amount of additive is between 0.1 and 10 weight-%, preferably between 1 and 5 weight-% calculated as part of the weight of the material.

Bio-based binders developed in Task 3.3 were not used for this specific application because it was not possible to obtain them in powder form for application in airlad equipment available at TP facility.

About the thermal resistance and conductivity, the obtained values for insulation materials used for building and automotive components didn't show significant variations respect to reference material (1-5% for rigid and soft panels).

It can be concluded that the material produced from 100% waste fibres without addition of binder presented notably lower strength than the reference material, whilst the absorption capability was totally in line with that of the reference material. With the addition of binder and with 40% mixing in of waste fibres, the final material is expected to show equivalent values for physical and mechanical properties respect to the reference material.

3.2 Sustainable binders for non wovens layers realization

Different sustainable binders were taken into account in order to satisfy market expectations for building and furniture sectors. In particular, the idea was to realize panels gluing different non wovens layers obtained by thermal compression (thickness 3 mm).

Two bio-based binders have been taken into account:

- SILANBLOK SM (RECOLL INTERNATIONAL S.R.L. UNIPERSONALE)

Monocomponent modified silane adhesive without amine and isocyanate solvent, for bonding pre-finished multilayer parquet, with very low emission of volatile organic compounds.

- PARQUET 0160 GREEN LINE COMP. A (RECOLL INTERNATIONAL S.R.L. UNIPERSONALE)

Two-component, water-free epoxy-polyurethane adhesive for gluing wooden floors, concrete screeds or pre-existing non-absorbent floors (marble, tiles, palladian, wood substrates).

Different tests have been performed by gluing seven non wovens layers (sample B and sample C) to reach 21 mm thickness by compression at 21°C (6-7 days for GREEN LINE to obtain the max rigidity; 2-3 days for SILANBLOCK to obtain the max rigidity). In Figure 4 are reported sectional views of the two samples.

(A)

(B)

Figure 4 – Non wovens layers glued by (A) GREEN LINE and (B) SILANBLOCK (B) binders.

Mechanical properties have been tested for GREEN LINE sample compared to conventional materials (MDF and plywood) and reported in Table 3. Sample obtained with SILANBLOCK have shown less rigidity respect to the use of GREENLINE.

Table 3 – Mechanical properties for non wovens layers realization respect to conventional materials (thickness 3 mm).

Test	Standard	Unit	Non wovens layers	MFD	Plywood
Breaking load	UNI EN 310	N/mm ²	No breaking	17	32
Density	UNI EN 323	kg/m ³	660	800	520
Elastic module	UNI EN 310	MPa	1280	1360	1180 (trasversal) – 3690 longitudinal

Data obtained will be used to realize the final intermediates for prototypes manufacturing (D4.5 and D4.6).

3.3 Technical aspects related to polyester fibers for non wovens

Physical properties of polyester fibers are important while producing nonwoven materials. For example, the lengths of cut are adapted to the respective manufacturing procedure. Fibers are also available in different of luster and cross-sectional forms.

Among the bi-component fibers, polyester is the most used fiber. Because of its increasing strength and soft hand of the nonwoven fabric, polyester is used in continuous bi-component filaments having a sheath component made of linear low-density polyethylene (PE) and a core component made of polyester.

Most of the insulation and industrial products are manufactured from synthetic and inorganic fibers by dry- and wet-laid methods. Nonwoven polyester fiber mats are used to produce electrical insulation laminates and electrical tape backing appliances.

Polyester fiber composites are widely used as filtration media. The layers of composite structure give excellent tear strength, a smooth, fiber-free surface, and edge stability. These products supply higher filtration efficiencies than calendared spun-bonded media.

Polyester fibers are used inside seat cushions, back pillows, mattresses and waterbeds, decorative and throw pillows, outdoors furniture, and even hand-stuffed custom upholstery in fiberfill applications.

3.4 Key characteristics for non wovens fibers

Manufacturers have a wide range of fiber options when specifying nonwoven fabrics for the products they produce. While some applications are great for natural fibers like cotton, others might be better served with synthetic fibers such as polyester. When considering fibers, it is important to compare the attributes of a given fiber in light of the fabric characteristics you want your final product to have.

When choosing the nonwoven fiber for your application, there are five key fiber characteristics that should be considered:

1. Strength

If strength is an important feature for your finished product to have, synthetic fibers offer high tensile strength. High strength synthetic fibers can be blended with weaker fibers to create a durable bicomponent fiber nonwovens. Polyester filament or a polyester blend fiber are a great choice for strength because polyester nonwovens offer high density. Nonwovens that require strength include those used for medical and hygiene products, construction materials, telecom products, agricultural fabric, and more.

2. Temperature Resistance

A variety of fibers including cotton, rayon, polyester, and blend can be used to create nonwovens with resistance to temperature. Chemical bonding is highly effective for developing temperature resistant nonwovens. The process of chemical bonding involves the application of a chemical binder to join polyester and rayon fibers to impart unique and beneficial characteristics to nonwovens, such as temperature resistance.

3. Shape

For products that need to retain their shape, without shrinking, stretching, or creasing, polyester fibers offer the best option. Chemical bonding and bicomponent fibers can also be beneficial to impart characteristics such as resistance to washing or dry cleaning, resistance to aging, as well as superior flexibility and handling.

4. Absorbency

For the characteristics of superior absorption and release, with a high degree of comfort and softness, cotton fiber is a great choice. Rayon filament or rayon blend are natural fibers

derived from wood pulp, that offer high absorbency, softness, and comfortable finish. When durability is also required, other types of fibers can be treated or blended to create a hydrophilic nonwoven.

5. Sustainability

Naturally occurring fibers are the best choice for sustainable nonwoven products. Though natural fibers are considered to be more expensive, they can be made in a way that makes them very competitive with synthetic fiber products if you choose a supplier that is experienced in developing environmentally friendly nonwovens. As governmental regulatory pressures concerning the environment increase, manufacturers in a variety of industries are switching from synthetic fiber nonwovens to compostable or biodegradable fiber environmentally friendly and sustainable nonwovens.

4. Conclusions and final recommendations

High strength fibres do not essentially produce high strength nonwoven preforms, with all other parameters constant. The tensile properties of nonwoven-reinforced composites are mainly dependent upon fibre tensile properties and fibre segment orientation distribution.

In ECOBULK project, airlaid technology has demonstrate the possibility to create a fiber web formed by randomly oriented fibers with physical and mechanical properties in line for selected market applications. Though the tensile strength of the nonwoven preform does not markedly contribute to the tensile strength of the composite, the structural and dimensional modifications associated with increased levels of bonding such as greater fibre entanglement, fibre re-orientation, fabric density and fibre volume fractions can influence resulting mechanical properties.

Thermal compression of non-wovens panels have shown the possibility to obtain different prototypes thickness and hardness.

Re-manufacturing processes showed the possibility to use 60% of recycled fibers restoring the same mechanical performances of the first production cycle: the main reason was related to the addition of virgin fibers in order to overcome the fibers structural changes for the shredding step. The possibility to use a binder should be explored considering bio-based formulation instead of conventional compounds available from the market.

A key driver to improve the use of recycled fibers in products development, is due to reduce the costs associated with manufacturing of nonwovens and to minimize potentially negative effects on the environment because the market is pushing for many consumer products constructed using recycled constituents.

This report has collected all the relevant aspects related to the manufacture and re-manufacture after N-cycles of the nonwoven products in the three industrial lines through. Further discussion with industrial partners will be expected in order to investigate the best conditions for re-manufacturing options.

Finally, two bio-binders have been tested to glue different non wovens layers for market application in furniture and building sector. The best one in terms of mechanical properties has been selected for final prototypes manufacturing.

5. Next steps

Different panels were shipped to MICROCAB and FCBA for specific physical/mechanical tests. CONENOR is evaluating some panels for application in construction sector with possible end-users. The tests reports will be included in D4.5 and D4.6 due to the COVID-19 situation.

6. References

Epstein, M.; Shishoo, R. A new process for fabricating nonwoven fibrous-reinforced elastomer composites. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 1992, 45, 1693–1704

El-Shekeil, Y.; Sapuan, S.; Abdan, K.; Zainudin, E. Influence of fiber content on the mechanical and thermal properties of kenaf fiber reinforced thermoplastic polyurethane composites. *Mater. Des.* 2012, 40, 299–303

Andersson, C.-H.; Dartman, T.; Gredinger, P.; Asplund, J.; Strandqvist, H. Flexible composites, strength, deformation, and fracture processes. 1. Reinforcement structures and tensile strength. *Mech. Compos. Mater.* 1998, 34, 525–536.

Martin, N.; Davies, P.; Baley, C. Evaluation of the potential of three non-woven flax fiber reinforcements: Spunlaced, needlepunched and paper process mats. *Ind. Crop. Prod.* 2016, 83, 194–205

Epstein, M.; Shishoo, R. A new process for fabricating nonwoven fibrous-reinforced elastomer composites. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 1992, 45, 1693–1704